

Supervised Machine Learning for Coptic Dialect Identification

Peter Missael

Institute of Egyptology and Coptic Studies, University of Göttingen, Germany
peter.missael@stud.uni-goettingen.de

Abstract

Dialect identification plays a crucial role in understanding the linguistic and cultural nuances of the Coptic language, the last stage of Ancient Egyptian, an Afro-Asiatic language. Despite its historical significance, there has been limited research in this area. This study introduces a supervised machine learning approach to Coptic dialect identification, aiming to bridge this gap in linguistic research, by leveraging advanced feature engineering and multiple classification algorithms.

1. Introduction

Coptic is the final stage of Ancient Egyptian, an Afro-Asiatic language with over four millennia of attested text production (~3000 BCE – 1400 CE). It was the dominant spoken language of Egypt. Though it is no longer a vernacular language, it continues to be used as the liturgical language of the Coptic Church (cf. Loprieno 1995: 5–8; Grossman and Richter 2015).

The majority of surviving Coptic literature is religious in nature, encompassing biblical texts, hagiographies, monastic writings, homilies, exegetical works, and liturgical materials. Records of the Coptic language reveal multiple (main) dialects, arranged geographically from north to south: Bohairic, Fayyumic, Mesokemic, Sahidic, Lycopolitan, and Akhmimic. While some dialects are extensively documented and widely

studied, others remain significantly underrepresented.

2. Related Work

2.1 Machine Learning Models for Coptic

Most existing machine learning models focus on a single Coptic dialect, namely Sahidic, since the majority of Coptic literature is written in it. Smith and Hulden (2016) introduced an analyzer/glosser capable of processing a properly transliterated raw text and producing a series of glosses. Zeldes and Schroeder (2016) developed an NLP pipeline for Sahidic Coptic with the following components: segmentation, normalization, POS-tagging, lemmatization, language of origin detection (for loanwords), and syntactic parsing.

Recent advancements have leveraged neural networks and Large Language Models (LLMs) for various tasks: Levine et al. (2024) applied neural networks to predict Coptic characters in manuscript lacunae;¹ Saeed et al. (2024) developed an LLM-based machine translation system for Coptic \leftrightarrow Arabic and Coptic \leftrightarrow English; Wannaz and Miyagawa (2024) designed an LLM-powered translation model specifically for Coptic ostraca.

¹ See also Lincke 2021 and the references therein for an overview of OCR models for Coptic printed texts.

Despite these developments, no automatic identifier for Coptic dialects has been created.

2.2 Machine Learning in Language Varieties and Dialect Identification²

Supervised machine learning has been successfully applied to the identification of language varieties and closely related languages, yielding promising results. Notable examples include the classification of linguistic varieties in Italy (Jauhiainen et al. 2022), dialect identification in Cuneiform texts (Jauhiainen et al. 2019; Doostmohammadi and Nassajian 2019), and differentiation among varieties of English, Spanish, and Portuguese (Vaidya and Kane 2023).

Unsupervised machine learning algorithms approaches have also been explored. Goswami et al. (2020) developed an Unsupervised Deep Language and Dialect Identification (UDLDI) model for short texts in closely related languages, applying it to datasets spanning South African languages, Dravidian languages, and Swiss German dialects.

3. Data

The dataset consists of lemmatized literary texts from various Coptic dialects, written in Coptic Unicode (U+2C80 to U+2CFF). These texts were originally prepared by the late Wolf-Peter Funk (1943-2021), a linguist and Coptologist. The lemmas (i.e. morphemes) were first converted

into continuous text while preserving proper word separation. Punctuation, diacritics, and special characters were removed, and the texts were then segmented into sentences, each labeled according to its respective dialect. A major challenge in this dataset (henceforth: Dataset A) is its imbalance:³

Table 1: Distribution of dialects in Dataset A

Dialect	No. of sentences	%
sah	6709	28.67
boh	6437	27.51
mox	5916	25.28
fay	1956	8.36
eboh	1867	7.98
pth	515	2.2
Total	23400	100

This imbalance is expected to have a significant impact on the performance of the underrepresented dialects, as will be discussed later (§5).

To address the issue, the underrepresented classes (i.e. dialects) needed expansion through additional sentences. Since the corpus consists of historical texts, adding new material is typically dependent on either archaeological discoveries of new texts or digitizing new ones—both of which are labor-intensive. To mitigate the imbalance in the study, an updated version of the dataset (henceforth: Dataset B) was created, which incorporates new sentences generated from the existing ones in underrepresented dialects (fay, eboh, and pth) using a systematic reduction

² For a recent and detailed discussion on machine learning for detecting language varieties and closely related languages, see Jauhiainen et al. 2024.

³ Dialect Abbreviations: boh (Bohairic dialect), eboh (Early Bohairic dialect), fay (Fayyumic dialect), l4

(Lycopolitan dialect, variant L4), l6 (Lycopolitan dialect, variant L6), mox (Mesokemic dialect), pth (Proto-Theban dialect), sah (Sahidic dialect).

approach. This process involved removing one word at a time, until only two words remained:

Authentic sentence: $word_1 word_2 word_3 \dots word_{n-2} word_{n-1} word_n$
 Generated sentence₁: $word_2 word_3 \dots word_{n-2} word_{n-1} word_n$
 Generated sentence₂: $word_3 word_4 \dots word_{n-2} word_{n-1} word_n$
 ...
 Generated sentence_{n-3}: $word_{n-2} word_{n-1} word_n$
 Generated sentence_{n-2}: $word_{n-1} word_n$

For example, a six-word sentence would yield four additional sentences. Random selections from these newly generated sentences ensured that the total number of sentences per dialect reached approximately 6,000.

Additionally, the dataset was further augmented with sentences from two additional dialects, resulting in the following distribution:

Table 2: Distribution of dialects in Dataset B

Dialect	No. of sentences	%
sah	6676	14.68
l4	6455	14.2
boh	6392	14.06
fay	6201	13.64
eboh	6191	13.62
mox	5907	12.99
l6	5456	12
pth	2185	4.81
Total	45463	100

4. Methodology

Various supervised machine learning algorithms were explored for the multiclassification task. As input feature, a 1- to 2-gram TF-IDF (Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency)

representation was applied, with a maximum of 10,000 features.

To optimize performance, hyperparameters for each machine learning model were fine-tuned using grid search with 5-fold cross-validation. The models evaluated include Support Vector Machine (SVM), Multinomial Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression. Additionally, a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) was experimented with as a deep learning approach.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Dataset A

Across all models, precision ranged between 0.85 and 0.95 for most dialects.⁴ However, recall and F1-score exceeded 0.90 for the three most represented dialects (boh, mox, and sah), while the underrepresented dialects (fay, eboh, and pth) exhibited lower recall values, averaging around 0.70. Notably, Random Forest recorded the lowest recall, dropping 0.54 for fay, and 0.58 for pth.

The following table summarizes the performance of the different models trained on Dataset A:

Table 3: Performance of ML models trained on Dataset A

	Accuracy		F1-score	
	Training	Test	Macro	Weighted
SVM	0.97	0.91	0.86	0.90
Multinomial NB	0.95	0.92	0.88	0.92
Random Forest	0.98	0.87	0.81	0.87
Logistic Regression	0.98	0.91	0.86	0.91
RNN	0.93	0.93	0.89	0.92

⁴ Performance metrics and confusion matrices for all models are provided in Appendices 1 and 2 respectively.

5.2 Dataset B

Precision, recall, and F1-score improved across all models, generally reaching around 0.90 or higher, with some exceeding 0.95. However, the two newly introduced dialects exhibited lower values, around 0.80 or below, likely due to their high linguistic similarity, which makes classification more challenging.

Importantly, performance for the three previously underrepresented dialects showed a substantial increase. For instance, the F1-score for eboh, which was 0.75 for RNN trained on Dataset A, improved to 0.91 on Dataset B.

The following table summarizes the performance of models trained on Dataset B:

Table 4: Performance of ML models trained on Dataset B

	Accuracy		F1-score	
	Training	Test	Macro	Weighted
SVM	0.93	0.87	0.87	0.87
Multinomial NB	0.89	0.86	0.86	0.86
Random Forest	0.96	0.85	0.86	0.85
Logistic Regression	0.94	0.87	0.88	0.88
RNN	0.88	0.88	0.89	0.88

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that machine learning models can effectively identify Coptic dialects, even in a low-resource language setting. By generating additional data from existing sources, dialect representation can be enhanced, leading to improved classification performance for underrepresented varieties. Models trained on a balanced dataset consistently achieved superior

results, underscoring the importance of data pre-processing and augmentation in the identification of language varieties.

Beyond classification, these models offer promising directions for further refinement. They can be fine-tuned to identify additional (sub)dialects and enhance the differentiation of the existing ones. Moreover, they can serve as an initial step in a Coptic NLP pipeline or in research to identify the most characteristic features (words) in each dialect, particularly in texts which show influences from various dialects.

Acknowledgements

The dataset’s texts were digitized by the late Wolf-Peter Funk (1943-2021). Special thanks to Eliese-Sophia Lincke (Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin) and Daniel Werning (Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities) for their generosity in making these texts available for this study.

References

- Doostmohammadi, Ehsan and Minoos Nassajian. 2019. Investigating Machine Learning Methods for Language and Dialect Identification of Cuneiform Texts. In *Proceedings of the Sixth Workshop on NLP for Similar Languages, Varieties and Dialects*, pp. 188–193. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/W19-1420>.
- Goswami, Koustava, Rajdeep Sarkar, Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi, Theodorus Fransen, and John P. McCrae. 2020. Unsupervised Deep Language and Dialect Identification for Short Texts. In *Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Computational Linguistics*, pp. 1606–1617. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.coling-main.141>.

- Grossman, Eitan, and Tonio Sebastian Richter. 2015. The Egyptian-Coptic Language: Its Setting in Space, Time and Culture. In *Egyptian-Coptic Linguistics in Typological Perspective*, edited by Eitan Grossman, Martin Haspelmath, and Tonio Sebastian Richter, pp. 69–101. Empirical Approaches to Language Typology [EALT] 55. Berlin, München, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110346510.69>.
- Jauhiainen, Tommi, Heidi Jauhiainen, Tero Alstola, Krister Lindén. 2019. Language and Dialect Identification of Cuneiform Texts. In *Proceedings of the Sixth Workshop on NLP for Similar Languages, Varieties and Dialects*, pp. 89–98. <https://aclanthology.org/W19-1409/>.
- Jauhiainen, Tommi, Heidi Jauhiainen, and Krister Lindén. 2022. Italian Language and Dialect Identification and Regional French Variety Detection using Adaptive Naive Bayes. In *Proceedings of the Ninth Workshop on NLP for Similar Languages, Varieties and Dialects*, pp. 119–129. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.vardial-1.13/>.
- Jauhiainen, Tommi, Marcos Zampieri, Timothy Baldwin, and Krister Lindén. 2024. *Automatic Language Identification in Texts*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-45822-4>.
- Levine, Lauren, Cindy Li, Lydia Bremer-McCollum, Nicholas Wagner, and Amir Zeldes. 2024. Lacuna Language Learning: Leveraging RNNs for Ranked Text Completion in Digitized Coptic Manuscripts. In *Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on Machine Learning for Ancient Languages (ML4AL 2024)*, pp. 61–70. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.ml4al-1.8/>.
- Lincke, Eliese-Sophia. 2001. The State of the Affairs in Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for Coptic. In Carlos Gracia Zamacona and Jónatan Ortiz García (eds.), *Handbook of Digital Egyptology*. Monografias del Oriente Antiguo. Madrid: Universidad de Alcalá, pp. 139–164.
- Loprieno, Antonio. 1995. *Ancient Egyptian: A Linguistic Introduction*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Saeed, Muhammed, Asim Mohamed, Mukhtar Mohamed, Shady Shehata, and Muhammad Abdul-Mageed. 2024. From Nile Sands to Digital Hands: Machine Translation of Coptic Texts. In *Proceedings of the Second Arabic Natural Language Processing Conference*, pp. 298–308. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.arabicnlp-1.25>.
- Smith, Daniel and Mans Hulden. 2016. Morphological Analysis of Sahidic Coptic for Automatic Glossing. In *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'16)*, pp. 2584–2588. <https://aclanthology.org/L16-1411/>
- Vaidya, Ankit and Aditya Kane. 2023. Two-stage Pipeline for Multilingual Dialect Detection. In *Tenth Workshop on NLP for Similar Languages, Varieties and Dialects (VarDial 2023)*, pp. 222–229, Dubrovnik, Croatia. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.vardial-1.22>.
- Wannaz, Audric-Charles and So Miyagawa. 2024. Assessing Large Language Models in Translating Coptic and Ancient Greek Ostraca. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Natural Language Processing for Digital Humanities*, pp. 463–471. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.nlp4dh-1.44>.
- Zeldes, Amir and Caroline T. Schroeder. 2016. An NLP Pipeline for Coptic. In *Proceedings of the 10th SIGHUM Workshop on Language Technology for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, and Humanities*, pp. 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/W16-2119>.

Appendix 1: Performance Metrics of Machine Learning Models for Coptic Dialect Identification⁵

Dataset A:

Support Vector Machine

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.86	0.94	0.90
eboh	0.82	0.71	0.76
fay	0.95	0.69	0.80
mox	0.91	0.95	0.93
pth	0.91	0.73	0.81
sah	0.94	0.96	0.95
Accuracy			0.90
Macro Avg	0.90	0.83	0.86
Weighted Avg	0.90	0.90	0.90

Dataset B:

Support Vector Machine

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.89	0.88	0.89
eboh	0.91	0.89	0.90
fay	0.93	0.88	0.90
l4	0.85	0.79	0.82
l6	0.63	0.84	0.72
mox	0.93	0.86	0.89
pth	0.97	0.93	0.95
sah	0.93	0.89	0.91
Accuracy			0.87
Macro Avg	0.88	0.87	0.87
Weighted Avg	0.88	0.87	0.87

Multinomial Naïve Bayes

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.88	0.94	0.91
eboh	0.82	0.70	0.76
fay	0.94	0.77	0.84
mox	0.94	0.96	0.95
pth	1.00	0.72	0.84
sah	0.94	0.98	0.96
Accuracy			0.92
Macro Avg	0.92	0.84	0.88
Weighted Avg	0.92	0.92	0.92

Multinomial Naïve Bayes

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.75	0.88	0.81
eboh	0.89	0.89	0.89
fay	0.93	0.88	0.90
l4	0.87	0.81	0.84
l6	0.79	0.64	0.71
mox	0.88	0.90	0.89
pth	0.92	0.96	0.94
sah	0.90	0.94	0.92
Accuracy			0.86
Macro Avg	0.87	0.86	0.86
Weighted Avg	0.86	0.86	0.86

Random Forest

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.82	0.94	0.88
eboh	0.83	0.58	0.69
fay	0.92	0.54	0.68
mox	0.87	0.95	0.91
pth	0.94	0.64	0.76
sah	0.93	0.95	0.94
Accuracy			0.87
Macro Avg	0.88	0.77	0.81
Weighted Avg	0.88	0.87	0.87

Random Forest

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.89	0.85	0.87
eboh	0.90	0.87	0.89
fay	0.92	0.86	0.89
l4	0.86	0.74	0.80
l6	0.58	0.86	0.69
mox	0.92	0.83	0.88
pth	0.98	0.92	0.95
sah	0.92	0.89	0.90
Accuracy			0.85
Macro Avg	0.87	0.85	0.86
Weighted Avg	0.87	0.85	0.85

⁵ For dialect abbreviations see fn. 3.

Logistic Regression

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.87	0.94	0.90
eboh	0.81	0.71	0.76
fay	0.94	0.72	0.82
mox	0.92	0.95	0.94
pth	0.90	0.73	0.81
sah	0.94	0.97	0.95
Accuracy			0.91
Macro Avg	0.90	0.83	0.86
Weighted Avg	0.91	0.91	0.91

Logistic Regression

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.91	0.88	0.89
eboh	0.91	0.89	0.90
fay	0.92	0.89	0.90
14	0.87	0.80	0.83
16	0.64	0.85	0.73
mox	0.93	0.88	0.90
pth	0.97	0.93	0.95
sah	0.93	0.90	0.92
Accuracy			0.87
Macro Avg	0.88	0.88	0.88
Weighted Avg	0.88	0.87	0.88

Recurrent Neural Network

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.82	0.94	0.88
eboh	0.83	0.58	0.69
fay	0.92	0.54	0.68
mox	0.87	0.95	0.91
pth	0.94	0.64	0.76
sah	0.93	0.95	0.94
Accuracy			0.87
Macro Avg	0.88	0.77	0.81
Weighted Avg	0.88	0.87	0.87

Recurrent Neural Network

Dialect	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
boh	0.90	0.89	0.90
eboh	0.92	0.90	0.91
fay	0.93	0.89	0.91
14	0.86	0.83	0.85
16	0.68	0.81	0.74
mox	0.92	0.90	0.91
pth	0.99	0.93	0.96
sah	0.93	0.92	0.92
Accuracy			0.88
Macro Avg	0.89	0.88	0.89
Weighted Avg	0.89	0.88	0.88

Appendix 2: Confusion Matrices

Dataset A:

Dataset B:

